

Enhanced Emission from Boron-Vacancy Center in Rhombohedral Boron Nitride

Nasrin Estaji,¹ Ismaeil Abdolhosseini Sarsari,¹ Gergő Thiering,² and Adam Gali^{2,3,4,*}

¹*Department of Physics, Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan 84156-83111, Iran*

²*HUN-REN Wigner Research Centre for Physics, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary*

³*Department of Atomic Physics, Institute of Physics,
Budapest University of Technology and Economics,
Műgyetem rakpart 3., H-1111 Budapest, Hungary*

⁴*MTA-WFK Lendület "Momentum" Semiconductor Nanostructures Research Group, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary*

(Dated: March 24, 2026)

Various stacking combinations of the two-dimensional (2D) boron nitride (BN) honeycomb lattice can significantly modify the properties of the resulting 2D BN crystal. Here, we demonstrate through first-principles calculations that the brightness of the negatively charged boron-vacancy center (V_B^-) is enhanced by at least one order of magnitude in rhombohedral BN (rBN) compared to hexagonal BN (hBN), while the spin properties remain either comparable or even improved. This enhancement arises from the reduced symmetry of the crystal field in rBN. Our results suggest that room-temperature single-spin coherent control of V_B^- is feasible in rBN, enabling its application as a single-spin quantum sensor in this 2D host. These findings demonstrate that engineered stacking of BN layers provides a powerful means to tailor the properties of embedded quantum defects.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among two-dimensional (2D) semiconductors, boron nitride (BN) stands out for its wide band gap, excellent physicochemical stability, and mechanical robustness. In layered sp^2 BN, two stable polytypes are commonly encountered [1, 2]: hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) with the AA' stacking sequence and rhombohedral boron nitride (rBN) with ABC stacking, which has only recently been demonstrated experimentally [3–5]. The stacking sequence strongly influences the optical response and fine structure of BN crystals [2, 5]. Light-matter interaction in monolayer BN is intrinsically weak because of the limited interaction length of a single atomic layer, but it strengthens with increasing layer number [4]. In hBN, inversion symmetry suppresses nonlinear optical interactions between adjacent layers, whereas rBN lacks inversion symmetry and thus naturally supports coherent enhancement of nonlinear optical signals. Accordingly, rBN exhibits distinct advantages, including strong optical nonlinearity, interfacial ferroelectricity, and polarized second-harmonic generation (SHG), all arising from its broken centrosymmetry [4, 6]. This symmetry breaking may also enable new functionalities beyond nonlinear optics.

In the context of quantum technologies, the wide band gaps of 2D BN polytypes make them attractive hosts for color centers. The first isolated quantum emitters were reported in hBN in the visible [7–9] and ultraviolet (UV) [10] spectral regions. More recently, it was shown that ABC stacking in rBN can substantially modify the PL spectra of UV emitters, and that their spectroscopic fingerprints can be used to identify the rBN host polytype [5]. However, coherent spin control of these

UV emitters has not yet been reported, limiting their prospects as qubits for quantum sensing and quantum communication. Here we take a major step toward this goal and show that the lack of inversion symmetry in rBN can be exploited to markedly improve quantum control of embedded, optically addressable defect spins.

Optical initialization and readout of single spins have been reported for several visible quantum emitters in hBN [11–16]. However, the microscopic origin of these qubits remains under active investigation. Recent studies suggest that donor-acceptor pairs may underlie some of these spin-active emitters, with random separations between the constituent species [17–20], which makes deterministic defect engineering challenging. In contrast, the negatively charged boron vacancy (V_B^-) is a well-established optically addressable defect-spin system in hBN [21, 22], and its concentration can be engineered in a controlled manner [23]. At the same time, coherent control has so far been limited largely to ensembles, because V_B^- is intrinsically dim and has not been substantially brightened in optical cavities [24]. Its extremely low quantum efficiency ($< 0.1\%$) originates from the dipole-forbidden nature of the transition between the first triplet excited state and the ground state [25–27].

In this study, we analyze the photophysics of V_B^- in 2D BN and show that the lack of inversion symmetry in rBN can enhance its emission intensity relative to hBN. Our *ab initio* results predict an approximately two-orders-of-magnitude increase in the radiative decay rate, with coherent zero-phonon-line emission expected to be observable at cryogenic temperatures in the near-infrared. The simulated room-temperature fluorescence spectrum and the ground-state zero-field-splitting tensor reinforce the tentative assignment of a near-infrared color center to V_B^- in rBN [28]. Combined with our previous finding of a long spin-lattice relaxation time T_1 [29], these results establish V_B^- in rBN as a strong candidate for single-spin quantum sensing. More broadly, our work leverages

* gali.adam@wigner.hun-ren.hu

e level is filled by two electrons, yielding the $m_S = +1$ component of an $S = 1$ state. Because two a_1 and two e orbitals appear in the band gap, we label them by their energetic ordering in the spin-majority channel; spin polarization can reorder these levels in the spin-minority channel. All of these orbitals are localized on the three nitrogen dangling bonds adjacent to the vacancy.

Previous work on V_B^- in hBN [26] showed that several vacancy-localized orbitals with similar energies contribute to strongly correlated many-body excited states. Motivated by this, we investigate the excited-state manifold using many-body perturbation theory within the GW+BSE framework (Methods), which captures correlated excitations as superpositions of single-particle transitions which is an essential aspect for V_B^- in two-dimensional BN [26]. The GW+BSE calculations resolve the low-energy intra-defect excitations and provide the corresponding excitation energies. They also enable analysis of the character of each excited state via its excitonic composition (Fig. 1c) and yield the optical transition strengths from the ground state.

Throughout these calculations, the atomic geometry is fixed at the DFT-optimized ground-state structure; the resulting spectrum therefore corresponds to vertical excitation energies and neglects ionic relaxation upon photoexcitation (Fig. 1d). Consequently, the computed spectrum is not intended for direct quantitative comparison with experiment; instead, it provides a reliable map of the optically accessible transition pathways between the ground state and the relevant excited states.

We find that the first excited state can be described as a combination of $a_1 \rightarrow e^*$ and $e \rightarrow e^*$ hole-electron pairs which transforms as 3E , see Fig. 1c for visualization. In stark contrast to V_B^- in hBN with D_{3h} symmetry, this first excited state is optically allowed from the ground state with perpendicular polarization of photons in the optical transition with C_{3v} symmetry. The excitation wavelength of the first excited state falls in the near-infrared (NIR) region. As can be seen in the side views of Fig. 1e the planar symmetry is broken which is responsible for the observable optical transition in the NIR region. We identify another optically allowed state with parallel polarization of photons also in the NIR region, and finally another state in the visible wavelength region (green color) with perpendicular polarization of photons which has the strongest optical transition dipole moment (see Fig. 1d). The last optical transition also occurs in hBN for V_B^- that can be used to efficiently excite the defect in hBN. Our calculations imply that V_B^- in rBN can be excited in the NIR region too.

Next we focus on the lowest energy triplet excited state which provides luminescence upon appropriate illumination. According to GW+BSE results, the state has 3E symmetry which is a subject to Jahn-Teller distortion. We apply Δ SCF method within HSE DFT to compute the adiabatic potential energy surface (APES) of this excited state. To this end, we promoted an electron from the a_1 level to the e^* level in the spin-minority channel.

After self-consistent field procedure in the C_{3v} symmetry, the resulting hole orbital has broken symmetry and it shows a mixture of a_1 and e_x characters which implies an multiplet exciton excited state—similar to the GW+BSE result.

We then allowed the ions to relax to a lower symmetry which indeed occurs due to $e \otimes E$ Jahn-Teller (JT) effect. Our simulations reveal substantial JT distortion that lower the total energy by 0.21 eV in the 3E state. The barrier between different JT distorted configurations is 159 meV.

The phonon sideband in the luminescence spectrum is determined within the Huang-Rhys (HR) theory [30–36] (see the original theory in Ref. [58] and our implementation in Ref. 37 that is based on Ref. 33). We calculated the PL spectra of V_B^- in rBN at 4 K and 300 K (Fig. 2a). The defect shows strong room-temperature PL centered at $\lambda \approx 734$ nm (1.69 eV). The computed HR factor is $S^{\text{tot}} = 3.46$ which results in a relatively broad PL spectrum but the coherent zero-phonon-line (ZPL) peaks becomes visible at low temperatures. We note that the sideband originates predominantly from the Jahn-Teller (JT)-active modes transforming according to the E representation of the C_{3v} group, as indicated by the decomposition of the total Huang-Rhys factor S^{tot} into E (JT-active) and A_1 (totally symmetric) contributions, with $S_{A_1} = 0.52$ and $S_E = 3.12$, respectively (see Supplementary Figure 1 in Supplementary Note 1 for details). The computed PL spectrum agrees well with an observed one at room temperature [28] that was associated with V_B^- in rBN.

The corresponding radiative lifetime (τ_{rad}) is ~ 1 μs , estimated as

$$\Gamma_{\text{rad}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{rad}}} = \frac{n_D E_{\text{ZPL}}^3 \mu^2}{3\pi\epsilon_0 c^3 \hbar^4}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, c is the speed of light, $n_D = 2.1$ is the refractive index of rBN at the ZPL energy E_{ZPL} , and $\mu = 0.8$ Debye is the optical transition dipole moment of given transition utilizing GW+BSE level of theory. In hBN, planar symmetry breaking phonons render emission partially allowed with radiative lifetime of > 10 μs (e.g., Ref. 25) whereas the zero-phonon coherent emission is symmetry-forbidden [27]. In contrast, the lower C_{3v} symmetry of rBN allows a direct emission with at least one order of magnitude shorter radiative lifetime than that in hBN. This is the most important finding of our study which turns V_B^- addressable at single defect level in rBN.

2. Spin properties

The 3A_2 ground state's spin density is localized on the three nitrogen dangling bonds (see Supplementary Figure 2). The respective hyperfine constants are listed in Supplementary Tables 1 and 2. The C_{3v} crystal field

FIG. 2. Photoluminescence spectrum of V_B^- in rBN at 4 K and 300 K from HSE DFT calculations. Zero-phonon-line (ZPL) peak appears and structured phonon sideband at low temperature. We note that the computed ZPL peak could have an inaccuracy of about 0.1 eV so the computed spectrum may be shifted when directly compared to experimental data.

splits the $m_S = 0$ and $m_S = \pm 1$ manifolds of the triplet by dipolar spin-spin interactions. The calculated zero-field splitting parameter is $D = 3.44$ GHz which agrees well with that of a recently observed ODMR center in rBN ($D \approx 3.45$ GHz at room temperature) that was associated with V_B^- [28]. We simulated the respective continuous wave (cw) ODMR spectrum with using the calculated hyperfine tensors that we show at zero magnetic field and at 9 mT in Fig. 3 (see Supplementary Note 4 for details about simulation parameters). Both transitions exhibit resolved hyperfine splitting into seven lines, originating from the nuclear spins ($I = 1$) of three equivalent ^{14}N atoms adjacent to the vacancy in the rBN plane. The nearest-neighbor ^{14}N nuclei yield a splitting of $A_{zz} \approx 48.3$ MHz in the ground state. The hyperfine broadening of the cw-ODMR spectrum in the simulated spectrum and the broadening in the observed cw-ODMR spectrum remarkably well agree which reaffirms the identification of the ODMR center in rBN.

We note that the reduced symmetry may open new relaxation channels when compared to those for V_B^- in hBN. The calculated spin-lattice relaxation time for V_B^- in rBN is $T_1 \approx 25 \mu\text{s}$ at room temperature which is analyzed in detail in our previous study [29]. This indicates that V_B^- in rBN can be applied as a room temperature qubit.

We further note that by solving the $e \otimes E$ JT Hamiltonian [38] for the 3E excited state with the use of our developed code [39], we obtained a Ham reduction factor of 0.006, implying strong quenching of spin-orbit coupling and off-diagonal zero-field-splitting tensor components [40] due to electron-phonon interactions. As a consequence, the usual $D = 3/2D_{zz}$ component yields the energy splitting between $m_S = 0$ and $m_S = \pm 1$ levels in the 3E excited state. On the other hand, the com-

FIG. 3. Spin properties of V_B^- in rBN. (a) cw-ODMR spectra at 9 mT (0 mT inset) magnetic fields.

putation of the zero-field-splitting (ZFS) tensor is not straightforward with DFT due to the multi-determinant nature of the excited state (see Supplementary Note 3 for details). Nevertheless, we roughly estimate the D -constant of the lowest energy 3E state to be approximately $D_{\text{theory}}^{\text{ex}} \approx 1.5$ GHz. We note that this *ab initio* value is relatively close to the experimentally observed 2.1 GHz associated with the ZFS of the excited state of V_B^- in hBN [41–45]. Given the similarity of the ground-state ZFS of V_B^- in hBN and rBN, our results suggest that the excited-state ZFS of V_B^- in rBN should also be around 2.1 GHz.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have theoretically demonstrated that the rhombohedral polytype of boron nitride provides a unique environment in which the optical and spin properties of the negatively charged boron-vacancy center are markedly enhanced. By combining density functional theory and many-body perturbation theory, we revealed that symmetry reduction in rBN enables optically allowed transitions with radiative lifetimes on the order of microseconds and photoluminescence that makes the coherent emission visible at low temperatures. The predicted zero-field splitting and hyperfine structure are in excellent agreement with experimental observations, supporting the reliability of our approach.

Our results establish rBN as a promising host material for solid-state spin defects, overcoming the low brightness that has limited the usability of V_B^- centers in hBN. This finding introduces a materials design pathway where layer stacking is not merely a structural detail but a powerful degree of freedom to engineer the quantum properties of embedded defects. Such control opens new opportunities for realizing room-temperature single-spin quan-

tum sensors, scalable photonic devices, and hybrid van der Waals quantum technologies.

Future work that integrates the predictive insights from our calculations with experimental validation will be essential for advancing rBN-based quantum defect platforms. More broadly, our study underscores the potential of stacking engineering in two-dimensional materials as a general strategy for tailoring defect-based quantum systems.

IV. METHODS

We employed two complementary approaches—density functional theory (DFT) and many-body perturbation theory (MBPT) within the GW approximation—to describe the electronic structure of the V_B^- defect at different levels of theory. For the DFT calculations, a plane-wave basis set with a cutoff of 450 eV and PAW atomic potentials [46] were used as implemented in VASP [47, 48]. The convergence criteria for total energy and atomic forces were set to 10^{-4} eV and 0.01 eV/Å, respectively. Structural relaxations, excited-state calculations within constrained occupation DFT (or Δ SCF method) [49], hyperfine tensors [50], and spin–spin zero-field splitting (ZFS) tensors [51] as implemented by Martijn Marsman were obtained using the Heyd-Scuzeria-Ernzerhof (HSE) hybrid functional [52] with a 0.32 fraction of exact exchange. To eliminate spin contamination in spin–spin ZFS tensor, we applied the correction scheme of Ref. [53]. The supercell model consisted of a $9 \times 9 \times 1$ 486-atom rBN supercell embedding a single negatively charged boron vacancy. The optimized interlayer distance was 3.31 Å, obtained using the DFT-D3 dispersion correction method of Grimme [54]. Optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR) simulations were performed with the EASYSPIN software package [55].

Since excitation spectra based purely on DFT energy levels are not always reliable for comparison with experiment [56], we also employed MBPT within the GW approximation and the Bethe–Salpeter equation (BSE) to predict the optical properties of both defects and the host lattice. MBPT explicitly accounts for electron–hole interactions in the excited state, where the excited electron experiences the Coulomb potential of the remaining hole; these correlated excitations are described by a two-particle Green’s function that fulfills the BSE [57]. Due to the high computational cost of MBPT, we used a smaller $6 \times 6 \times 1$ 216-atom supercell, which is sufficient to avoid artificial defect–defect interactions from periodic replicas while maintaining convergence in excitation energies. For bulk pristine rBN, our GW+BSE calculations yielded a band gap of 5.82 eV at the K point, in good agreement with experiment [4, 58].

Quasiparticle energies were obtained within the $evGW_0$ scheme, starting from HSE DFT results as input. This method provides an efficient and accurate approximation to the GW formalism. Quasiparticle wave functions and energies were updated until convergence was reached after four iterations. A cutoff of 270 eV was sufficient for the GW calculations, including those with the V_B^- defect. For the self-energy calculations, 6500 bands were included. Brillouin-zone sampling was restricted to the Γ -point, which proved convergent for both DFT and GW+BSE calculations. The defect-level energy differences obtained from GW were consistent with those from HSE (see Supplementary Note 5), validating their reliability for subsequent BSE optical property calculations.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All data included in this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

CODE AVAILABILITY

All code included in this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A.G. acknowledges access to high-performance computational resources provided by KIFÜ (Governmental Agency for IT Development, Hungary) and funding from the European Commission for the SPINUS (Grant No. 101135699) and QuSPARC (Grant No. 101186889) projects. G.T. acknowledges the STARTING Grant No. 150113 from the National Office of Research, Development and Innovation of Hungary (NKFIH) and the support from the János Bolyai Research Scholarship of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences. N.E. acknowledges the scholarship support from the Iranian Ministry of Science, Research, and Technology. This work is based upon research funded by the Iranian National Science Foundation (INSF) under project No. 4021945.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

N.E. and G.T. performed the computations. The analysis of the results was carried out by N.E., supervised by I.A.S., G.T., and A.G. A.G. conceived and supervised the project. All authors contributed to manuscript writing.

[1] W. Olovsson and M. Magnuson, Rhombohedral and turbostratic boron nitride polytypes investigated by x-ray

absorption spectroscopy, *The Journal of Physical Chem-*

- istry C **126**, 21101 (2022).
- [2] M. Zanfagnini, A. Plaud, I. Stenger, F. Fossard, L. Sponza, L. Schué, F. Paleari, E. Molinari, D. Varsano, L. Wirtz, *et al.*, Distinguishing different stackings in layered materials via luminescence spectroscopy, *Physical Review Letters* **131**, 206902 (2023).
 - [3] M. Moret, A. Rousseau, P. Valvin, S. Sharma, L. Souqui, H. Pedersen, H. Högberg, G. Cassaboïs, J. Li, J. Edgar, *et al.*, Rhombohedral and turbostratic boron nitride: X-ray diffraction and photoluminescence signatures, *Applied Physics Letters* **119** (2021).
 - [4] J. Qi, C. Ma, Q. Guo, C. Ma, Z. Zhang, F. Liu, X. Shi, L. Wang, M. Xue, M. Wu, P. Gao, H. Hong, X. Wang, E. Wang, C. Liu, and K. Liu, Stacking-controlled growth of rbn crystalline films with high nonlinear optical conversion efficiency up to 1%, *Advanced Materials* **36**, 2303122 (2024).
 - [5] J. Iwański, K. P. Korona, M. Tokarczyk, G. Kowalski, A. K. Dąbrowska, P. Tatarczak, I. Rogala, M. Bilska, M. Wójcik, and S. Kret, Revealing polytypism in 2d boron nitride with uv photoluminescence, *npj 2D Materials and Applications* **8**, 72 (2024).
 - [6] L. Wang, J. Qi, W. Wei, M. Wu, Z. Zhang, X. Li, H. Sun, Q. Guo, M. Cao, Q. Wang, C. Zhao, Y. Sheng, Z. Liu, C. Liu, M. Wu, Z. Xu, W. Wang, H. Hong, P. Gao, M. Liu, Z.-J. Wang, X. Xu, E. Wang, F. Ding, X. Zheng, K. Liu, and X. Bai, Bevel-edge epitaxy of ferroelectric rhombohedral boron nitride single crystal, *Nature* **629**, 74 (2024).
 - [7] T. T. Tran, K. Bray, M. J. Ford, M. Toth, and I. Aharonovich, Quantum emission from hexagonal boron nitride monolayers, *Nature Nanotechnology* **11**, 37 (2016).
 - [8] Z. Shotan, H. Jayakumar, C. R. Considine, M. Mackoït, H. Fedder, J. Wrachtrup, A. Alkauskas, M. W. Doherty, V. M. Menon, and C. A. Meriles, Photoinduced Modification of Single-Photon Emitters in Hexagonal Boron Nitride, *ACS Photonics* **3**, 2490 (2016).
 - [9] L. J. Martínez, T. Pelini, V. Waselowski, J. R. Maze, B. Gil, G. Cassaboïs, and V. Jacques, Efficient single photon emission from a high-purity hexagonal boron nitride crystal, *Physical Review B* **94**, 121405 (2016).
 - [10] R. Bourrellier, S. Meuret, A. Tararan, O. StÅ©phan, M. Kociak, L. H. G. Tizei, and A. Zobelli, Bright UV Single Photon Emission at Point Defects in h-BN, *Nano Letters* **16**, 4317 (2016).
 - [11] N. Chejanovsky, A. Mukherjee, J. Geng, Y.-C. Chen, Y. Kim, A. Denisenko, A. Finkler, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, D. B. R. Dasari, P. Auburger, A. Gali, J. H. Smet, and J. Wrachtrup, Single-spin resonance in a van der Waals embedded paramagnetic defect, *Nature Materials* **20**, 1079 (2021), number: 8.
 - [12] H. L. Stern, Q. Gu, J. Jarman, S. Eizagirre Barker, N. Mendelson, D. Chugh, S. Schott, H. H. Tan, H. Siringhaus, I. Aharonovich, and M. Atatüre, Room-temperature optically detected magnetic resonance of single defects in hexagonal boron nitride, *Nature communications* **13**, 618 (2022).
 - [13] N.-J. Guo, S. Li, W. Liu, Y.-Z. Yang, X.-D. Zeng, S. Yu, Y. Meng, Z.-P. Li, Z.-A. Wang, L.-K. Xie, R.-C. Ge, J.-F. Wang, Q. Li, J.-S. Xu, Y.-T. Wang, J.-S. Tang, A. Gali, C.-F. Li, and G.-C. Guo, Coherent control of an ultrabright single spin in hexagonal boron nitride at room temperature, *Nature Communications* **14**, 2893 (2023).
 - [14] R. N. Patel, R. E. K. Fishman, T.-Y. Huang, J. A. Gusdorff, D. A. Fehr, D. A. Hopper, S. A. Breitweiser, B. Porat, M. E. Flatté, and L. C. Bassett, Room Temperature Dynamics of an Optically Addressable Single Spin in Hexagonal Boron Nitride, *Nano Letters* **24**, 7623 (2024).
 - [15] H. L. Stern, C. M. Gilardoni, Q. Gu, S. Eizagirre Barker, O. F. J. Powell, X. Deng, S. A. Fraser, L. Follet, C. Li, A. J. Ramsay, H. H. Tan, I. Aharonovich, and M. Atatüre, A quantum coherent spin in hexagonal boron nitride at ambient conditions, *Nature Materials* , 1 (2024).
 - [16] X. Gao, S. Vaidya, K. Li, Z. Ge, S. Dikshit, S. Zhang, P. Ju, K. Shen, Y. Jin, Y. Ping, and T. Li, Single nuclear spin detection and control in a van der Waals material, *Nature* **643**, 943 (2025).
 - [17] P. Auburger and A. Gali, Towards ab initio identification of paramagnetic substitutional carbon defects in hexagonal boron nitride acting as quantum bits, *Phys. Rev. B* **104**, 075410 (2021).
 - [18] S. Li, A. Pershin, and A. Gali, Quantum emission from coupled spin pairs in hexagonal boron nitride, *Nature Communications* **16**, 5842 (2025).
 - [19] I. O. Robertson, B. Whitefield, S. C. Scholten, P. Singh, A. J. Healey, P. Reineck, M. Kianinia, G. Barcza, V. Ivády, D. A. Broadway, I. Aharonovich, and J.-P. Tetienne, A charge transfer mechanism for optically addressable solid-state spin pairs, *Nature Physics* , 1 (2025).
 - [20] B. Whitefield, H. Z. J. Zeng, J. Liddle-Wesolowski, I. O. Robertson, A. Ganyecz, V. Ivády, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, M. Toth, J.-P. Tetienne, I. Aharonovich, and M. Kianinia, Narrowband quantum emitters in hexagonal boron nitride with optically addressable spins, *Nature Materials* **25**, 412 (2026).
 - [21] M. Abdi, J.-P. Chou, A. Gali, and M. B. Plenio, Color Centers in Hexagonal Boron Nitride Monolayers: A Group Theory and Ab Initio Analysis, *ACS Photonics* **5**, 1967 (2018).
 - [22] A. Gottscholl, M. Kianinia, V. Soltamov, S. Orlinskii, G. Mamin, C. Bradac, C. Kasper, K. Krambrock, A. Sperlich, M. Toth, I. Aharonovich, and V. Dyakonov, Initialization and read-out of intrinsic spin defects in a van der waals crystal at room temperature, *Nature materials* **19**, 540 (2020).
 - [23] P. Udvarhelyi, T. Clua-Provost, A. Durand, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, B. Gil, G. Cassaboïs, V. Jacques, and A. Gali, A planar defect spin sensor in a two-dimensional material susceptible to strain and electric fields, *npj Computational Materials* **9**, 1 (2023), number: 1.
 - [24] J. E. Fröch, L. P. Spencer, M. Kianinia, D. D. Totonjian, M. Nguyen, A. Gottscholl, V. Dyakonov, M. Toth, S. Kim, and I. Aharonovich, Coupling Spin Defects in Hexagonal Boron Nitride to Monolithic Bullseye Cavities, *Nano Letters* **21**, 6549 (2021).
 - [25] J. R. Reimers, J. Shen, M. Kianinia, C. Bradac, I. Aharonovich, M. J. Ford, and P. Piecuch, Photoluminescence, photophysics, and photochemistry of the vb-defect in hexagonal boron nitride, *Physical Review B* **102**, 144105 (2020).
 - [26] V. Ivády, G. Barcza, G. Thiering, S. Li, H. Hamdi, J.-P. Chou, Ö. Legeza, and A. Gali, Ab initio theory of the negatively charged boron vacancy qubit in hexagonal boron nitride, *npj Computational Materials* **6**, 41 (2020).
 - [27] F. Libbi, P. M. M. de Melo, Z. Zanolli, M. J. Verstraete, and N. Marzari, Phonon-assisted luminescence in defect

- centers from many-body perturbation theory, *Physical Review Letters* **128**, 167401 (2022).
- [28] A. Gale, M. Kianinia, J. Horder, C. Tweedie, M. Singhal, D. Scognamiglio, J. Qi, K. Liu, C. Verdi, I. Aharonovich, and M. Toth, Quantum Emitters in Rhombohedral Boron Nitride, *Advanced Optical Materials* **13**, e00593 (2025), eprint: <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/adom.202500593>
- [29] N. Estaji, I. A. Sarsari, G. Thiering, and A. Gali, Spin-phonon relaxation of boron-vacancy centers in two-dimensional boron nitride polytypes, arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.00154 (2025).
- [30] K. Huang and A. Rhys, Theory of light absorption and non-radiative transitions in f-centres, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **204**, 406 (1950).
- [31] R. Kubo and Y. Toyozawa, Application of the method of generating function to radiative and non-radiative transitions of a trapped electron in a crystal, *Progress of Theoretical Physics* **13**, 160–182 (1955).
- [32] M. de Jong, L. Seijo, A. Meijerink, and F. T. Rabouw, Resolving the ambiguity in the relation between stokes shift and huang–rhys parameter, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **17**, 16959–16969 (2015).
- [33] A. Alkauskas, B. B. Buckley, D. D. Awschalom, and C. G. Van de Walle, First-principles theory of the luminescence lineshape for the triplet transition in diamond nv centres, *New Journal of Physics* **16**, 073026 (2014).
- [34] Y. Jin, M. Govoni, G. Wolfowicz, S. E. Sullivan, F. J. Heremans, D. D. Awschalom, and G. Galli, Photoluminescence spectra of point defects in semiconductors: Validation of first-principles calculations, *Physical Review Materials* **5**, 084603 (2021).
- [35] M. Lax, The franck-condon principle and its application to crystals, *The Journal of chemical physics* **20**, 1752 (1952).
- [36] P. Kehayias, M. W. Doherty, D. English, R. Fischer, A. Jarmola, K. Jensen, N. Leefer, P. Hemmer, N. B. Manson, and D. Budker, Infrared absorption band and vibronic structure of the nitrogen-vacancy center in diamond, *Phys. Rev. B* **88**, 165202 (2013).
- [37] A. Gali, T. Demján, M. Vörös, G. Thiering, E. Cannuccia, and A. Marini, Electron–vibration coupling induced renormalization in the photoemission spectrum of diamondoids, *Nature Communications* **7**, 10.1038/ncomms11327 (2016).
- [38] G. Thiering and A. Gali, Ab initio calculation of spin-orbit coupling for an nv center in diamond exhibiting dynamic jahn-teller effect, *Physical Review B* **96**, 081115 (2017).
- [39] B. Toth, A. Gali, and G. Thiering, Exe.py: Ab initio fine structure parameters for trigonal defect qubits within the e[−]e[−] jahn-teller case (2025), arXiv:2512.05704 [cond-mat.mtrl-sci].
- [40] G. Thiering and A. Gali, Nuclear-spin relaxation in solid-state-defect quantum bits via electron-phonon coupling in the optically excited state, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **24**, 044027 (2025).
- [41] N. Mathur, A. Mukherjee, X. Gao, J. Luo, B. A. McCullian, T. Li, A. N. Vamivakas, and G. D. Fuchs, Excited-state spin-resonance spectroscopy of $v_{\bar{b}}$ defect centers in hexagonal boron nitride, *Nature Communications* **13**, 10.1038/s41467-022-30772-z (2022).
- [42] S. Baber, R. N. E. Malein, P. Khatri, P. S. Keatley, S. Guo, F. Withers, A. J. Ramsay, and I. J. Luxmoore, Excited state spectroscopy of boron vacancy defects in hexagonal boron nitride using time-resolved optically detected magnetic resonance, *Nano Letters* **22**, 461–467 (2021).
- [43] P. Yu, H. Sun, M. Wang, T. Zhang, X. Ye, J. Zhou, X. Wang, F. Shi, Y. Wang, and J. Du, Excited-state spectroscopy of spin defects in hexagonal boron nitride, *Nano Letters* **22**, 3545–3549 (2022).
- [44] Z. Mu, H. Cai, D. Chen, J. Kenny, Z. Jiang, S. Ru, X. Lyu, T. S. Koh, X. Liu, I. Aharonovich, and W. Gao, Excited-state optically detected magnetic resonance of spin defects in hexagonal boron nitride, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **128**, 216402 (2022).
- [45] X. Gao, S. Vaidya, K. Li, P. Ju, B. Jiang, Z. Xu, A. E. L. Allcca, K. Shen, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, S. A. Bhave, Y. P. Chen, Y. Ping, and T. Li, Nuclear spin polarization and control in hexagonal boron nitride, *Nature Materials* **21**, 1024–1028 (2022).
- [46] P. E. Blöchl, Projector augmented-wave method, *Physical review B* **50**, 17953 (1994).
- [47] G. Kresse and J. Hafner, Ab initio molecular-dynamics simulation of the liquid-metal–amorphous-semiconductor transition in germanium, *Physical Review B* **49**, 14251 (1994).
- [48] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Physical review B* **54**, 11169 (1996).
- [49] A. Gali, E. Janzén, P. Deák, G. Kresse, and E. Kaxiras, Theory of spin-conserving excitation of the n-v-center in diamond, *Physical review letters* **103**, 186404 (2009).
- [50] K. Szász, T. Hornos, M. Marsman, and A. Gali, Hyperfine coupling of point defects in semiconductors by hybrid density functional calculations: The role of core spin polarization, *Phys. Rev. B* **88**, 075202 (2013).
- [51] Z. Bodrog and A. Gali, The spin–spin zero-field splitting tensor in the projector-augmented-wave method, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **26**, 015305 (2013).
- [52] J. Heyd, G. E. Scuseria, and M. Ernzerhof, Hybrid functionals based on a screened coulomb potential, *The Journal of chemical physics* **118**, 8207 (2003).
- [53] T. Biktagirov, W. G. Schmidt, and U. Gerstmann, Spin decontamination for magnetic dipolar coupling calculations: Application to high-spin molecules and solid-state spin qubits, *Physical Review Research* **2**, 022024 (2020).
- [54] S. Grimme, J. Antony, S. Ehrlich, and H. Krieg, A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (dft-d) for the 94 elements h-pu, *The Journal of chemical physics* **132** (2010).
- [55] S. Stoll and A. Schweiger, Easyspin, a comprehensive software package for spectral simulation and analysis in epr, *Journal of magnetic resonance* **178**, 42 (2006).
- [56] C. Attacalite, M. Bockstedte, A. Marini, A. Rubio, and L. Wirtz, Coupling of excitons and defect states in boron-nitride nanostructures, *Physical Review B—Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **83**, 144115 (2011).
- [57] G. Onida, L. Reining, and A. Rubio, Electronic excitations: density-functional versus many-body green’s-function approaches, *Reviews of modern physics* **74**, 601 (2002).
- [58] L. Sponza, H. Amara, C. Attacalite, S. Latil, T. Galvani, F. Paleari, L. Wirtz, and F. Ducastelle, Direct and indirect excitons in boron nitride polymorphs: A story of

atomic configuration and electronic correlation, Physical Review B **98**, 125206 (2018).

- [59] M. J. Rayson and P. R. Briddon, First principles method for the calculation of zero-field splitting tensors in periodic systems, Phys. Rev. B **77**, 035119 (2008).

Supplemental Material

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 1: APPLICATION OF HUANG-RHYS THEORY

Within the Huang-Rhys (HR) theory, one takes the following approximations:

- Both the ground and excited states exhibit the same parabolic confinement potential with the same set of vibration modes: $(\hbar\omega_i)$, where $i = 1 \dots (3N - 3)$ spans all vibration modes of a rBN supercell hosting N atoms.
- The electron-phonon coupling manifests itself only by that these two adiabatic potential energy surfaces (APES) are shifted from each other by a fixed amount by $2\alpha_i$.

Optical transitions are accompanied by phonon sidebands. The corresponding lineshape can be described within the model of two displaced quantum harmonic oscillators. Because the minima of the two potential energy surfaces are displaced relative to each other, not only the zero-phonon-line (ZPL) transition is allowed, but transitions involving different phonon quanta also acquire finite intensity due to the nonzero overlap of their vibrational wavefunctions. The square of this dimensionless displacement is known as the partial Huang-Rhys (HR) factor, $S_i = 2\alpha_i^2$, which characterizes the strength of the electron-phonon coupling for each vibrational mode. Accordingly, the potential energy surfaces of the ground and excited electronic states, $V_-(x_i)$ and $V_+(x_i)$, can be written in terms of the dimensionless normal coordinates x_i as follows:

$$V_{\mp}(x_i) = \mp \frac{\Delta}{2} + \sum_i \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_i}{2} x_i^2 \mp f_i x_i \right) = \mp \frac{\Delta}{2} + \sum_i \frac{\hbar\omega_i}{2} \left(x_i \mp \frac{f_i}{\hbar\omega_i} \right)^2 - \frac{f_i^2}{(\hbar\omega_i)^2}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where Δ is the bare electronic excitation energy. The quantity f_i is the derivative of the total energy with respect to the normal coordinate, i.e., the generalized force experienced by the system upon electronic excitation. By completing the square, one finds that the dimensionless displacement is given by $\alpha_i = f_i/(\hbar\omega_i)$. In *ab initio* calculations, however, the static displacement is typically obtained in Å units, which allows the shift in generalized coordinates to be computed as follows [33]:

Next, the generalized coordinates q_i provide a convenient way to define the Huang-Rhys factors S_i (or, equivalently, the dimensionless displacements α_i):

$$S_i = \frac{\omega_i q_i^2}{2\hbar} \quad \text{or} \quad 2\alpha_i = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_i}{\hbar}} q_i. \quad (\text{S2})$$

These quantities allow the zero-temperature lineshape function to be written as follows (see the Supplementary Material of Ref. [36] for details):

$$F(\hbar\omega, T = 0 \text{ K}) = \sum_{i, \nu_i} \left| \langle 0_i^{(g)} | \nu_i^{(e)} \rangle \right|^2 \delta \left(\hbar\omega - \sum_{\nu_i} \nu_i \hbar\omega_i \right) = e^{-S_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{\text{tot}}^n}{n!} I_n(\hbar\omega). \quad (\text{S3})$$

Here, $|\nu_i^{(e)}\rangle$ denotes the vibrational wavefunction of the excited state with ν_i phonon quanta, whereas $\langle 0_i^{(g)}|$ denotes the vibrational wavefunction of the ground state with zero phonon quanta. The functions $I_n(\hbar\omega)$ are defined recursively by convolution,

$$I_n(\hbar\omega) = \int d(\hbar\omega') I_{n-1}(\hbar\omega') S(\hbar\omega - \hbar\omega'). \quad (\text{S4})$$

Finally,

$$S(\hbar\omega) = I_1(\hbar\omega) = \sum_i S_i \delta(\hbar\omega - \hbar\omega_i) \quad (\text{S5})$$

is the Huang-Rhys spectral function, which determines the first phonon sideband, whereas the zero-phonon line is given by

$$I_0(\hbar\omega) = \delta(\hbar\omega), \quad (\text{S6})$$

and the total Huang–Rhys factor is

$$S_{\text{tot}} = \sum_i S_i. \quad (\text{S7})$$

At finite temperature ($T > 0$), it is convenient to use the generating-function formalism based on the Fourier transform pair $S(\hbar\omega) \leftrightarrow S(t)$. The generating function is then defined as

$$G(t) = e^{S(t)-S(0)}, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where

$$S(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [n(\hbar\omega)e^{+i\omega t} + (n(\hbar\omega) + 1)e^{-i\omega t}] S(\hbar\omega) d(\hbar\omega), \quad (\text{S9})$$

and

$$n(\hbar\omega) = \left[\exp\left(\frac{\hbar\omega}{k_B T}\right) - 1 \right]^{-1} \quad (\text{S10})$$

is the Bose–Einstein occupation factor for the vibrational quanta. The temperature-dependent lineshape function is then given by

$$F(\hbar\omega, T) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} G(t) e^{i\omega t - \gamma|t|} dt \quad (\text{S11})$$

where γ may be chosen to reproduce the experimental broadening of the ZPL.

One must still distinguish between the cases of photoluminescence (PL) and absorption (A):

$$I_{\text{PL}}(\hbar\omega, T) = (\hbar\omega)^3 F(\Delta_{\text{ZPL}} - \hbar\omega, T) \quad \text{and} \quad I_{\text{A}}(\hbar\omega, T) = (\hbar\omega) F(\Delta_{\text{ZPL}} + \hbar\omega, T), \quad (\text{S12})$$

where Δ_{ZPL} is the zero-phonon transition energy. Thus, the PL and absorption lineshapes are weighted by factors of $(\hbar\omega)^3$ and $(\hbar\omega)^1$, respectively.

We additionally note that the Stokes shift, i.e., the difference between the vertical absorption and vertical emission energies, can be written as follows [32]:

$$E_{\text{Stokes}} = \underbrace{V_+(\alpha_i) - V_-(\alpha_i)}_{\text{vertical absorption}} - \underbrace{[V_+(-\alpha_i) + V_-(-\alpha_i)]}_{\text{vertical emission}} = \left(\Delta + \sum_i \hbar\omega_i S_i \right) - \left(\Delta - \sum_i \hbar\omega_i S_i \right) \approx 2S_{\text{tot}} \hbar\langle\omega_i\rangle, \quad (\text{S13})$$

where $\langle\omega_i\rangle$ denotes the S_i -weighted mean vibrational frequency,

$$\langle\omega_i\rangle = \frac{\sum_i S_i \omega_i}{S_{\text{tot}}}. \quad (\text{S14})$$

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 2: HYPERFINE TENSORS

Calculated values of the hyperfine coupling constants for nitrogen and boron nuclear spins are presented in Tables SI and SII, respectively, for the most significant neighboring sites of VB, see Supplementary Figure 2(a). Since the hyperfine interaction with farther nuclear spins is much weaker, we only consider the nearest nuclear spins. The spin density of the excited state shows a reduction of symmetry as shown in Supplementary Figure 2(b).

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 3: DETERMINATION OF ZFS TENSORS

Determination of ZFS tensors

The zero-field-splitting (ZFS) tensor for a two-particle wavefunction

$$|\psi_i \psi_j\rangle = \frac{\psi_i(r_1)\psi_j(r_2) - \psi_j(r_1)\psi_i(r_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (\text{S15})$$

Supplementary Figure 1. Partial Huang-Rhys factors individually distributed into totally symmetric A_1 and Jahn-Teller active E modes at 0 K temperature.

Supplementary Figure 2. Calculated spin density. (a) Ground state. (b) Excited state. The vacant boron site located in the middle layer of rBN is depicted as a semitransparent green ball.

constructed from orbitals ψ_i and ψ_j with the same spin projection (e.g. both \uparrow) can be calculated as follows, including exchange effects [51, 59]:

$$D^{(ij)} = \frac{3}{2}D_{zz}^{(ij)} = \left\langle \psi_i \psi_j \left| \frac{3}{2}f_{zz} \right| \psi_i \psi_j \right\rangle = \frac{3}{2} \left(\langle \psi_i(r_1) \psi_j(r_2) | f_{zz}(r_1 - r_2) | \psi_i(r_1) \psi_j(r_2) \rangle - \langle \psi_i(r_1) \psi_j(r_2) | f_{zz}(r_1 - r_2) | \psi_j(r_1) \psi_i(r_2) \rangle \right), \quad (\text{S16})$$

where

$$f_{ab}(r) = \frac{r^2 \delta_{ab} - 3r_a r_b}{r^5} \quad (\text{S17})$$

is the magnetic dipole-dipole kernel, with $a, b \in \{x, y, z\}$ denoting Cartesian coordinates and $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$.

At this point, we consider a C_{3v} -symmetric ZFS tensor, which has only one independent parameter:

$$D_{ab} = \begin{pmatrix} D_{xx} & D_{xy} & D_{xz} \\ D_{xy} & D_{yy} & D_{yz} \\ D_{xz} & D_{yz} & D_{zz} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} -D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -D & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2D \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

Therefore, it is sufficient to evaluate the D_{zz} tensor element. For simplicity, the physical constants μ_B and g are omitted.

This simplification becomes especially relevant for the $|^3E\rangle$ excited state, where orbital degeneracy can in principle induce off-diagonal elements in D_{ab} . However, these effects are expected to be absent even at low temperatures for V_B^- in rBN because of strong electron-phonon interaction (see the small Ham reduction factor). As a consequence, only the splitting between the $m_S = \pm 1$ and $m_S = 0$ sublevels remains, which can then be parametrized by a single ZFS constant D .

Supplementary Table 1. *Ab initio* hyperfine parameters for ^{14}N nuclei $I = 1$ nuclear spins in the negatively charged boron-vacancy in rBN. All hyperfine values are in MHz unit.

site	A_{xx}	A_{yy}	A_{zz}	A_{xy}
N_1	80.566	57.865	48.304	19.670
N_1	80.584	57.873	48.329	-19.669
N_1	46.505	91.924	48.303	0.005
N_2	6.699	4.484	4.372	0.594
N_2	5.553	5.628	4.371	1.256
N_2	6.694	4.480	4.364	-1.255
N_2	6.694	4.480	4.364	-0.593
N_2	4.522	6.659	4.371	0.660
N_2	4.524	6.659	4.372	-0.662
N_3	0.830	0.172	-0.398	0.000
N_3	0.335	0.665	-0.399	0.286
N_3	0.336	0.666	-0.398	-0.285
N_4	0.315	0.367	0.246	0.101
N_4	0.439	0.237	0.242	0.029
N_4	0.262	0.414	0.242	-0.073
N_4	0.266	0.415	0.246	0.073
N_4	0.442	0.240	0.247	-0.029
N_4	0.316	0.367	0.247	-0.102

Supplementary Table 2. *Ab initio* hyperfine parameters for ^{11}B nuclei with $I = 3/2$ nuclear spins in the negatively charged boron-vacancy in rBN. All hyperfine values are in MHz unit.

site	A_{xx}	A_{yy}	A_{zz}	A_{xy}
B_1	-1.740	5.358	-4.326	0.899
B_1	-1.740	5.358	-4.326	-0.899
B_1	2.805	0.813	-4.326	3.523
B_1	2.805	0.813	-4.326	-3.523
B_1	4.362	-0.744	-4.326	2.624
B_1	4.362	-0.744	-4.326	-2.624
B_2	-1.213	0.167	-1.651	0.000
B_2	-0.178	-0.868	-1.651	0.597
B_2	-0.178	-0.868	-1.651	-0.597
B_3	2.920	2.057	1.725	-0.446
B_3	1.885	3.090	1.724	0.151
B_3	1.886	3.090	1.725	-0.151
B_3	2.920	2.057	1.725	0.446
B_3	2.658	2.317	1.724	0.597
B_3	2.659	2.318	1.725	-0.597
B_4	-0.977	-0.272	-1.196	0.000
B_4	-0.447	-0.800	-1.195	-0.306
B_4	-0.448	-0.801	-1.196	0.305

More generally, for an N -electron system, the ZFS tensor can be evaluated as a sum over occupied spin orbitals. For example, for the $|^3A_2^{\text{gnd}}\rangle$ state of V_{B}^- ,

$$D_{\text{gnd}} = \frac{1}{S(2S-1)} \sum_{i,j}^{\text{occ.}} D^{(ij)}, \quad (\text{S19})$$

where the sum runs over all occupied orbitals in both spin channels. In the present case,

$$i, j \in \{\text{VB orbitals}, a_1^\uparrow, a_1^\downarrow, a_1^{*\uparrow}, a_1^{*\downarrow}, e_x^\uparrow, e_x^\downarrow, e_y^\uparrow, e_y^\downarrow, e_x^{*\downarrow}, e_y^{*\downarrow}\}, \quad (\text{S20})$$

as depicted in Fig. 1b of the main text. We emphasize that the sum must also include all valence-band (VB) orbitals. By contrast, the orbitals $\{e_x^{*\uparrow}, e_y^{*\uparrow}\}$ are unoccupied and therefore do not enter the sum. For triplet states ($S = 1$), the prefactor $1/[S(2S-1)]$ is equal to unity.

We compute the ZFS tensor using the implementation in VASP 5.4.1 as implemented by Martijn Marsman. For the two-hole configuration

$$|^3A_2^{\text{gnd}, m_S=+1}\rangle = |e_x^{\star\uparrow} e_y^{\star\uparrow}\rangle, \quad (\text{S21})$$

accessible within our DFT approach, we obtain

$$D_{\text{ZFS}}[|e_x^{\star\uparrow} e_y^{\star\uparrow}\rangle] = 2627 \text{ MHz}. \quad (\text{S22})$$

As noted in the main text, we employ the spin-decontamination scheme proposed in Ref. 53, which requires evaluation of the ZFS for the broken-symmetry singlet configuration:

$$D[|e_y^{\star\uparrow} e_x^{\star\downarrow}\rangle] = -4250 \text{ MHz}. \quad (\text{S23})$$

In this case, the prefactor $1/[S(2S-1)]$ must be removed from the VASP source code to avoid division by zero.

The corrected ground-state ZFS is then obtained by averaging the ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic solutions, taking into account the sign change of the latter:

$$D_{\text{theory}}^{\text{gnd}} = \frac{1}{2} (D[|e_x^{\star\uparrow} e_y^{\star\uparrow}\rangle] - D[|e_x^{\star\uparrow} e_y^{\star\downarrow}\rangle]) = \frac{1}{2} (2627 \text{ MHz} + 4250 \text{ MHz}) = 3438 \text{ MHz}. \quad (\text{S24})$$

This value is remarkably close to the experimentally observed room-temperature value,

$$D_{\text{expt.}}^{\text{gnd}} \approx 3.45 \text{ GHz}, \quad (\text{S25})$$

which supports the plausibility of the correction scheme for V_{B}^- .

Tentative derivation of the ZFS for the $|^3E\rangle$ excited multiplet

We first construct the symmetry-adapted wavefunctions for the ground and excited multiplets:

$$\begin{aligned} |^3A_2^{\text{gnd}}\rangle &= |e_x^{\star} e_y^{\star}\rangle, \\ |^3A_1\rangle &= (|e_x e_x^{\star}\rangle + |e_y e_y^{\star}\rangle)/\sqrt{2}, \quad |^3E_x\rangle = a|a_1 e_x^{\star}\rangle + b(-|e_x e_x^{\star}\rangle + |e_y e_y^{\star}\rangle) + c|a_1^{\star} e_x^{\star}\rangle, \\ |^3A_2\rangle &= (|e_x e_y^{\star}\rangle - |e_y e_x^{\star}\rangle)/\sqrt{2}, \quad |^3E_y\rangle = a|a_1 e_y^{\star}\rangle + b(|e_x e_y^{\star}\rangle + |e_y e_x^{\star}\rangle) + c|a_1^{\star} e_y^{\star}\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S26})$$

For simplicity, the \uparrow spin labels are omitted. According to our GW+BSE results, the expansion coefficients are $a^2 = 0.57$, $2b^2 = 0.32$, and $c^2 = 0.07$, as shown in Fig. 1c of the main text. Here, $|^3E_{x,y}\rangle$ refers to the lower $|^3E\rangle$ multiplet. The $|^1A_1\rangle$ level lies well above the upper $|^3E\rangle$ state, is optically inactive, and appears at 2.35 eV.

Because we cannot evaluate the ZFS directly on top of the GW+BSE wavefunctions, we instead use Δ SCF calculations. In this approach, we obtain the following two values entering the decontamination correction:

$$D_{\Delta\text{SCF}}^{\text{ex.}} = \frac{1}{2} (D[\Psi_{\Delta\text{SCF}}^{\uparrow\uparrow}] - D[\Psi_{\Delta\text{SCF}}^{\uparrow\downarrow}]) = \frac{1}{2} (-564 \text{ MHz} + 3579 \text{ MHz}) = 1508 \text{ MHz}, \quad (\text{S27})$$

where

$$\Psi_{\Delta\text{SCF}}^{\uparrow\uparrow} \approx |aa_1^{\uparrow} + be_x^{\uparrow} + ca_1^{\star\uparrow}; e_y^{\star\uparrow}\rangle \quad (\text{S28})$$

and

$$\Psi_{\Delta\text{SCF}}^{\uparrow\downarrow} \approx |aa_1^{\uparrow} + be_x^{\uparrow} + ca_1^{\star\uparrow}; e_y^{\star\downarrow}\rangle \quad (\text{S29})$$

are the single-Slater-determinant triplet and broken-symmetry singlet Δ SCF solutions, respectively, approximately representing the $|^3E_y\rangle$ triplet.

Thus, we identify the Δ SCF component of $|^3E_y\rangle$ as

$$|^3E_y\rangle = \underbrace{|aa_1 + ca_1^{\star} + be_x; e_y^{\star}\rangle}_{\sqrt{1-b^2} \Psi_{\Delta\text{DFT}}^{\uparrow\uparrow}} + b|e_y e_x^{\star}\rangle. \quad (\text{S30})$$

For simplicity, we neglect the multiconfigurational contribution $b|e_y e_x^{\star}\rangle$ when estimating the excited-state ZFS.

Supplementary Figure 3. Visualization of the broken symmetry Kohn-Sham orbital $|aa_1^\uparrow + be_x^\uparrow + ca_1^{*\uparrow}\rangle$ that of (a) $\Psi_{\Delta SCF}^{\uparrow\uparrow}$ in Eq. (S28) and (b) $\Psi_{\Delta SCF}^{\uparrow\uparrow}$ in Eq (S29).

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 4: EASYSPIN CODE

We generate Fig. 3 of the main text by the following Easyspin code:

```
clear

Sys.S = 1; % two electrons spin with S=1/2
Sys.g = 2; % isotropic g for two electron spins
%Sys.lw= 10.0; % Gaussian Isotropic broadening
Sys.HStrain = [10 10 10]; %Gaussian FWHM Anisotropic broadening in all directions [MHz]
%(For hyperfine splittings)
Sys.D= [3450 10]; %MHz [D E]
Sys.A = [4.362 -0.744 -4.326; ... %11B hyperfine tensors: Axx, Ayy, Azz
         4.362 -0.744 -4.326; ... %11B.
         2.805 0.813 -4.326; ... %11B
         2.805 0.813 -4.326; ... %11B
         -1.74 5.358 -4.326; ... %11B
         -1.74 5.358 -4.326; ... %11B
         80.566 57.865 48.312; ... %14N
         46.506 91.925 48.304; ... %14N
         80.566 57.865 48.304]; %14N %MHz

Sys.Nucs = '11B, 11B, 11B, 11B, 11B, 11B, 14N, 14N, 14N';
Exp.Field = 9; %mT
Exp.Temperature = 4; %kelvin
Exp.mwRange = [3 4]; %GHz
%Exp.mwFreq = [];
Exp.CrystalSymmetry= 'C3v';
Exp.MolFrame = [0 0 0];
Exp.SampleFrame = [0 0 0]; %sample aligned with lab frame
%Exp.CrystalOrientation = [0 0 1];
Exp.nPoints = 1500;
%Exp.Range = [0 100];
%Opt.Method = 'perturb1';
%Opt.Verbosity = 1;

Opt.Method = 'hybrid';
Opt.HybridCoreNuclei = [7 8 9]; % these atoms treated exactly and others perturbatively

pepper(Sys,Exp,Opt);
```

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 5: COMPARISON OF EVGW0 AND DFT-HSE LEVELS

In Supplementary Table 3 we list the quasiparticle and Kohn-Sham levels in the Γ -point for the 216-atom $6 \times 6 \times 1$ supercell. The results imply that the DFT-HSE spectrum is a good starting point for the excited state calculation by

the Δ SCF method.

Supplementary Table 3. The evGW0 quasiparticle (DFT-HSE) levels in the Γ -point are given in eV unit as obtained in 216-atom supercell.

\uparrow orb.	value (eV)	occ.	\downarrow orb.	value (eV)	occ.
VBM	0.89(1.13)	1	VBM	0.89(1.13)	1
a_1^\uparrow	0.89(1.13)	1	a_1^\downarrow	1.53(1.71)	1
e_x^\uparrow	1.48(1.29)	1	e_x^\downarrow	1.47(1.72)	1
e_y^\uparrow	1.48(1.29)	1	e_y^\downarrow	1.47(1.72)	1
$a_1^{*\uparrow}$	1.16(1.42)	1	$a_1^{*\downarrow}$	2.32(1.81)	1
$e_x^{*\uparrow}$	1.26(1.50)	1	$e_x^{*\downarrow}$	5.56(5.70)	0
$e_y^{*\uparrow}$	1.26(1.50)	1	$e_y^{*\downarrow}$	5.56(5.70)	0
CBM	7.61(7.13)	0	CBM	7.61(7.13)	0